

INFLUENCE OF DEPRESSANT ADDITIVES ON CRUDE OIL FUEL**Aliyev S.,***Docent, Candidate of Chemical Sciences, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University***Mammadzada A.***Master's degree student, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University***Abstract**

This study investigates the optimization of low-temperature diesel fuel properties through the utilization of depressant additives. Two depressant additives, K-ES and D-315, are assessed for their efficacy in improving Cold Filter Plugging Point (CFPP) and Pour Point (PP) of diesel fuels sourced from different manufacturers. Methodologically, optimal additive dosages and introduction temperatures are determined through comprehensive testing of fuel samples. Results reveal distinct behaviors of the additives, with both K-ES and D-315 exhibiting concentration-dependent effects on low-temperature properties. Notably, D-315 demonstrates superior performance at higher concentrations, significantly reducing freezing and filtration temperatures. Molecular composition and solvent characteristics are identified as critical factors influencing additive effectiveness. Overall, this study provides valuable insights into the selection and application of depressant additives, essential for ensuring efficient engine operation in challenging environmental conditions.

Keywords: diesel fuel, depressant additives, low-temperature properties, CFPP, PP.

Introduction

Climate conditions necessitate a high demand for high-quality low-temperature diesel fuels. One solution to this problem is the production of low-temperature diesel fuels. [1]

Considering the presence of technologically isolated regions and decentralized energy supply, obtaining diesel fuel with improved low-temperature properties based on summer grades by introducing depressant additives is one of the current tasks in addressing the issues of diesel equipment operation.

Diesel fuel from different manufacturers has different characteristics and requires an individual approach in selecting additives.

The main indicator of diesel fuel performance in an engine is the Cold Filter Plugging Point (CFPP). The Pour Point (PP), simulating warehouse storage conditions of diesel fuel, is not regulated in current diesel fuel standards, and modern depressant additives do not affect the cloud point temperature. [2]

The effectiveness of depressant additives largely depends on the composition of diesel fuel and its characteristics. Fuels with different characteristics have different abilities to "receive" (accept) depressants, and this is a very important aspect of additive application. The main parameter we consider is the principle of the depressant's action on paraffin crystals. Based on this, we evaluate the interaction of the additive with the fractional and group hydrocarbon composition of diesel fuels and the influence on the physicochemical characteristics of the paraffins themselves contained in the fuel. [3] [4]

It has been noted on numerous occasions that diesel fuels with wide boiling ranges are more susceptible to depressants than fuels with narrow fractional compositions. For this reason, depressant additives differ in their sensitivity to the fractional composition of fuels. [5]

Purpose of the research

The purpose of this study is to optimize the low-temperature properties of diesel fuels by evaluating the efficacy of depressant additives, addressing the challenges posed by diverse climate conditions and decentralized energy infrastructures. This research aims to assess the impact of depressant additives on Cold Filter Plugging Point (CFPP) and Pour Point (PP) of diesel fuels from various manufacturers. Methodologically, the study determines optimal dosages and introduction temperatures of two depressant additives, K-ES and D-315, through comprehensive testing of fuel samples. The main objective is to provide valuable insights into the selection and application of depressant additives, essential for ensuring efficient engine operation in challenging environmental conditions.

Experimental part

Two additives were tested as depressants: K-ES and D-315.

The physicochemical characteristics of these additives were discussed in Chapter 2 (please add the table from Chapter 2).

Considering the natural-climatic conditions of equipment operation in the North, the main indicators for low-temperature diesel fuel from crude oil were selected: [6]

Cold Filter Plugging Point (CFPP)

Pour Point.

The optimal dosage introduction temperature of the additive is approximately 10°C higher than the cloud point temperature.

Initially, the optimal concentration of the depressant added to the diesel fuel was selected, based on subsequent determination of its low-temperature properties.

In the study, 12 samples of diesel fuel containing additive K-ES at concentrations ranging from 0.10% to 0.50% by mass, and additive D-315 at concentrations ranging from 0.10% to 0.7% by mass, were prepared and tested. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the influence of these additives on the low-temperature properties of the diesel fuels.

Figure 1. Dependence of freezing temperature and freezing point depression on the concentration of depressant additive K-ES.

Figure 1. Dependence of freezing temperature and freezing point depression on the concentration of depressant additive D-315

Results and Discussion

From the provided data, it can be seen that the behavior characteristics of depressor additives are not similar. At concentrations of 0.1, 0.2, and 0.5% by mass in the fuel containing the mentioned additives, an improvement in low-temperature indicators is observed, but with an increase in the concentration of the K-ES additive, low-temperature indicators deteriorate. Depressor additive D-315 significantly improves low-temperature indicators sufficiently well at the concentrations mentioned above, but at concentrations exceeding 0.55% by mass, the freezing and filtration temperatures increase. It is worth noting that both additives effectively reduce the freezing and filtration

temperatures. For the K-ES additive, the maximum reduction in the freezing temperature (from -28°C to -39°C) and the pour point temperature (from -17°C to -25°C) is achieved at a concentration of 0.2% by mass. The maximum reduction in the freezing temperature for the diesel fraction (from -28°C to -53°C) and the pour point temperature (from -17°C to -39°C) of the investigated diesel fraction samples is achieved with the introduction of 0.55% by mass of the D-315 additive into the fraction.

The active substance in both used additives is a copolymer of vinyl acetate with alkyl methacrylate, but its content and solvents for commercial diesel fuels are different. Perhaps these differences in the behavior of

the two additives in the fuel obtained from the Talakan oil field can be explained by the concentration in the commercial form (the content of the active substance in the K-ES additive is 60-75%, in the D-315 additive - 70-85%). Also, the behavior of additives depends on the mutual molecular weight distribution of monomeric units in the polymer molecule (the ratio of ethylene and vinyl acetate units). The solvent also plays an important role, affecting the structural and volumetric state of the polymer molecule: "ball" or "thread".

From the presented data, it is evident that both additives exhibit a higher depressor effect in fuel derived from the gasoline fraction of crude oil. At a minimum concentration of 0.1% by mass of the aforementioned additives, as shown in Figure 3, the fuel freezing temperature, depending on the additive introduced into it, ranges from -36°C to -45°C , and the maximum filtration temperature ranges from -20°C to -33°C . In terms of effectiveness, all investigated additives can be ranked in the following order: D-315 and K-ES.

Figure 2. Influence of the investigated additives introduced into the diesel fraction at a 0.1% concentration on its low-temperature properties.

The maximum reduction in the freezing temperature for the diesel fraction (from -28°C to -53°C) and the pour point temperature (from -17°C to -39°C) of the investigated diesel fraction samples is achieved with the introduction of 0.55% by mass of the Difron 315 additive into the fraction. Thus, the obtained results allowed identifying the most optimal concentrations of the additives under consideration in the fuel. For the K-ES additive, this concentration was 0.2% by mass, and for the D-315 additive, it was 0.55% by mass. [7]

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